

Acetoacetarylamides as Chelating Ligands, Part-III. Copper (II) Chelates*

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Methods of preparation of the complexes of the type (CuL_2) and $(CuXL_2)$, where LH=acetoacetarylamides (aceto-acetanilide, aceto-acet-ortho-chloroanilide, aceto-acetanisidide and aceto-acet-orthotoluidide), X=pyridine, have been described. Electrolytic conductance measurements in methanol indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The complexes are all paramagnetic (1.7-1.8 B.M.). The electronic absorption spectra exhibits two ligand field bands around $18,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $14,500\text{-}16,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes of the type (CuL_2) and only one band in the vicinity of $15,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes of the type $(CuXL_2)$. Magnetic moment and electronic absorption spectra identify the first category of complexes as square planar and the second as distorted octahedral ones.

In the previous papers in this series, the hexa-coordinated complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) acetoacetarylamides with aromatic heterocyclic N-bases were described^{1,2}. This communication describes the tetra-coordinated complexes of copper(II) with acetoacetarylamides (aceto-acetanilide, acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide, aceto-acetanisidide and aceto-acet-orthotoluidide) and quinque-coordinated adducts of copper(II) bis acetoacetarylamides with pyridine.

The $3d^9$ copper(II) complexes are subject to a considerable Jahn-Teller effect resulting in mostly distorted tetrahedral or distorted octahedral structures³. The dark blue copper(II) acetylacetonate is one of the very few exceptions giving rise to square-planar configuration⁴. It is desired to prepare (a) copper(II) complexes of acetoacetarylamides which have close relation to acetylacetonate¹, (b) the adducts of copper(II) bis acetoacetarylamides with aromatic heterocyclic amines and to investigate their structure. The preparation of copper(II) bis aceto-acetanilide was reported long ago⁵. However, nothing has so far appeared on the structure of this complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper (II) chloride dihydrate was a B.D.H.'s product. Pyridine, 2-methylpyridine were Hopkin & William's (England) product. Aceto-acetanilide, aceto-acet ortho-chloroanilide, acetoacet-anisidide and acetoacet-orthotoluidide were B.D.H.'s L.R. variety and were used directly. Methanol used was of E. Merck's G. R. variety.

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3. C. J. Ballhausen, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", Mc Graw-Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, 1962, p-268.

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General method of preparation:

METHOD-I. For complexes of the type (CuL_2) : Copper (II) chloride dihydrate (0.002M) was dissolved in water. Acetoacetarylamide (0.004M) was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol. These two solutions were mixed and pH of the mixture was adjusted to 5 with dilute ammonium hydroxide. Addition of few ml. of water gave green to olive-green precipitates which were filtered off, recrystallised from acetone and dried in air.

The complexes are insoluble in water and benzene but soluble in dioxan, chloroform, methanol, acetone and pyridine.

METHOD-II. For complexes of the type $(CuXL_2)$: Copper (II) chloride dihydrate (0.002M) was dissolved in water. Acetoacetarylamide (0.004M) was dissolved in alcoholic pyridine. These two solutions were then mixed and pH of the solution was adjusted to 7 with dilute ammonium hydroxide. Addition of few ml. of water led to the formation of green crystals. These were filtered off, washed with 1:1 ethanol and dried in air.

The complexes are in general insoluble in water, benzene, chloroform but soluble in methanol and ethanol. These are very stable, do not lose the heterocyclic base even on heating at 120° for hours.

Procedure: Electrolytic conductance measurements were done with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in the region 10,000-25,000 cm^{-1} in Hilger Watts Uvispek Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells. Magnetic measurements were taken in a Gouy Balance using G.R. $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as the calibrant. Copper was estimated by igniting the complex to oxide, then dissolving with conc. HCl and finally titrating iodometrically with sodium thiosulphate. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas semimicro combustion technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the method of preparation of complexes of the type $(CuXL_2)$, it is likely that addition of ammonium hydroxide favours the pH for the introduction of heterocyclic base to copper(II) bis acetoacetarylamide. 2-methylpyridine does not form well-defined crystalline adducts which may be ascribed to the possible steric hindrance offered by the 2-methyl group. While the corresponding adducts of cobalt (II) and nickel(II) bis acetoacetarylamides are six-coordinated^{1,2}, the copper (II) adducts are five-coordinated. This observation is in line with the corresponding acetylacetonate complexes^{6,7}. Attempts to prepare six-coordinated adducts did not quite materialise.

Electrolytic conductance measurements of these complexes were performed in methanol at 31° (conc. 0.005M) and low molar conductance values indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes (table-I.)

The magnetic moments of all copper(II) complexes are in the range 1.6-2.2 B.M., with the exception of subnormal values observed for the presence of metal-metal interaction. The measured room temperature magnetic moments of these complexes are close to the spin only value (table I) which supports a planar or tetragonally distorted octahedral

6. H. M. N. H. Irving and N. S. Al-Ni'imi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1671.

7. W. H. Walker and N. C. Li, *ibid.*, 1965, **27**, 2255 and references therein.

configuration rather than a tetrahedral stereochemistry. Magnetic moments of tetrahedral copper(II) complexes are higher than the spin only value due to some orbital contribution⁸. It seems likely that any kind of metal-metal interaction is absent in these chelates.

TABLE I

Analysis, Molar conductance, Magnetic susceptibility and Electronic absorption spectral data of the Complexes

Complex	Analytical data		Molar Conduc- tance mhos	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Wave number ν , cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity litre mole cm^{-1}
	Found%	Reqd%				
1. [Cu (Ace-anil) ₂]	Cu, 15.2	15.3	4.1	1.75	18,350 ^a { 16,600- 14,280	33 35.5
	N, 6.8	6.7				
2. [Cu (Ace-Cl-anil) ₂]	Cu, 12.8	13.0	4.2	1.79	18,520 ^a { 16,390 14,490	32 35
	N, 5.6	5.7				
3. [Cu (Ace-anis) ₂]	Cu, 13.0	13.2	3.9	1.78	18,350 ^a { 16,660 14,490	32.5 sh 36
	N, 5.9	5.8				
4. [Cu (Ace- γ -tol) ₂]	Cu, 14.2	14.2	5.1	1.81	18,350 ^a { 16,390 14,300	32.5 35.5
	N, 6.3	6.2				
5. [Cu Py (Ace-anil) ₂]	Cu, 12.6	12.8	5.0	1.82	{ 15,620 ^b 14,920	56.5
	N, 5.6	5.6				
6. [Cu Py (Ace-Cl-anil) ₂]	Cu, 11.3	11.2	4.5	1.85	{ 15,620 ^b 14,920	56
	N, 5.0	4.9				
7. [Cu Py (Ace-anis) ₂]	Cu, 11.3	11.4	4.0	1.82	{ 15,620 ^b 14,920	58
	N, 5.1	5.0				
8. [Cu Py (Ace-o-tol) ₂]	Cu, 12.2	12.0	4.1	1.87	{ 15,620 ^b 14,920	55
	N, 5.2	5.3				

where Ace-o-anil=acetoacetanilide, Ace-Cl-anil=acetoacet-orthochloroanilide, Ace-anis=aceto-acetanilide, Ace-o-tol=aceto-acet-ortho-toluidide and Py=pyridine.

'a' means chloroform solution, 'b' means mixed alcohol solution (methanol, ethanol, 1:1).

Sh=shoulder.

The existence of a planar or tetrahedral ligand field results in the presence of three bands, which may appear in the form of a very broad asymmetric band, due to the transitions $^3 2B_{2g} \leftarrow 2B_{1g}$, $2E_g \leftarrow 2B_{1g}$ and $2A_{1g} \leftarrow 2B_{1g}$. Tetragonal distortion also splits the d_{xy} and the d_{xz} levels resulting in three expected d-d transitions. Most distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes exhibit asymmetric contours, which have been resolved in few cases to two or three overlapping and symmetrical bands⁸. Any d-d band due to planar or distorted octahedral structure occurs at higher energy (around 19,000 cm^{-1} for planar complexes and around 15,000-18,000 cm^{-1} for octahedral complexes) than those in a pseudo-tetrahedral arrangement (around 8,000-11,500 cm^{-1})⁹⁻¹⁰. The electronic spectra of copper(II) bis acetoacetylarnides are of the type found for planar complexes with four oxygen

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donors^{6,7,11-13}. The quinque-coordinated pyridine adducts exhibit a single intense band around $15,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and it is reasonable in the above light to assign them distorted octahedral structures with four oxygen atoms in the xy-plane, and pyridine on or close to the z-axis. The disappearance of the band around $550\text{ m}\mu$ due to the bis acetoacetarylamine copper(II), the increase in intensity around $660\text{ m}\mu$, and the clear isobestic point, all confirm that only two species are involved. The band positions suggest that the ligand field of bis acetylacetonato copper(II), which shows two broad bands^{11,12} at 535 and $660\text{ m}\mu$, is stronger than those of bis acetoacetarylamine copper(II).

Thermal dissociation studies of these complexes are in progress and will be published in due course.

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